

Business Management Concept Evaluation in the Context of Public Relationship

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Abstract

Public relations in a strategic sense are addressed in three dimensions : in the order , at the level of functionality strategy , and at the level of operations . at the level of social strategy , public relations is a process that focuses on social relations , establishes a balance between business aims and social responsibility , and emphasizes a sustainability target audience and stakeholder connection _ Corporate governance , a strategic communication strategy based on mutually beneficial relationships between corporations and society , is commonly consider as a function of public relations _ Of this study , general information regarding " business management " and " public relations " functions is provided , along with exhaustive explanations and an analysis of their interrelationships .

Keywords : *Management of Organizations , Business Management, Public Relationship*

1. Introduction

The system, which did not care about the human element in the classical management understanding in the 1800s, started to value people over time. The increase in the factor of people in organizations has led them to become more successful when they are successful, and to earn more when they are earning. This has caused corruption, selfishness, and dissatisfaction in organizations. Therefore, this change in the order has caused changes in the organizational sense, and although it was a concept that was only mentioned in books until 20 years ago, it has led to the use of the concept of "business management", which has now become the most talked about concept in the organizational field.

The size of today's organizations, the increase in competition, technological innovations and providing access to the markets all over the world from where we sit have made it difficult to control and manage organizationally. The growth of the markets has increased the investor

needs of the organizations and has caused them to meet the concepts of share and stakeholder. Such changes in organizations cause them to take control again, to gain confidence in the competitive environment, and to turn to corporate governance in order to grow more.

This concept, created by the changing understanding of organizational management in the developing world order, is the whole of activities for organizations to be transparent, fair, accountable and fulfill their responsibilities. It aimed to protect the shares and stakeholders in order to prevent the corruption scandals of the organization, especially in large-scale organizations, the ambitions of the managers and the dissatisfaction of the people. The Sarbanes-Oxley law was enacted in the USA for governance, which has become a problem in the world, it was accepted as the "OECD Principles" in 1999 and has started to take its place in the CMB since 2003 in our country. Rules and principles that are expected to be followed in Turkey were published and organizations were expected to comply with these principles and rules. They were expected to make publications on this issue regularly every year.

While organizations grow so much and need their target audiences so much with the effect of technology, they need to give equal importance to public relations. Public relations, which are indispensable both for their communication with their shareholders and stakeholders and for the target audience, are of great importance in terms of corporate governance.

Corporate governance, which is a strategic communication process based on mutual benefit relations between organizations and society, is known to be considered as a function of public relations. In this research, general information about "business management" and "public relations" functions are given and comprehensive explanations are given, and the relations between these two concepts are evaluated.

2. General Information

Within the scope of the research, the concepts of business management and public relations are discussed:

2.1. Business Administration

The emergence of business management was caused by corruption in the accounting and reporting of organizational activities by large-scale organizations in the early 2000s, which shook public confidence. Hearing of such events damaged the public's trust in the financial order. This development has led to a change in the focus of organizations and an increase in the presence of stakeholders. This division of management in organizations and the inclusion of new shareholders in the organization increased the responsibilities towards them and public trust. These responsibilities are: the principle of equality (fairness), the principle of transparency, the principle of accountability and the principle of responsibility (Tutar, 2015; Karakılıç & Vuran, 2019; TKYD, 2021; SPK, 2021; Coşkun & Akcan, 2018; TÜSİAD, 2000).

There are many reasons why organizations adopt the concept of corporate governance, which can be shaped according to the institutional structures of organizations. Despite this flexible structure of the concept, it has two main aims that are accepted by everyone. These are the performance of the organization and the harmony between the parties of the organization.

2.1.1. Objectives of Business Management

to maximize the operational efficiency and long-term profit expectations of the shareholders and stakeholders, to increase the motivation of the organization, to provide economic welfare and to distribute them within the organization. The secondary purpose is that the harmony between these parties involved in the management of the organization and its positive reflections on the organization will increase the financial gains and organizational trust of the organization. It is an expected behavior to prevent a share or one of the stakeholders from committing corruption, unethical behavior, misuse of organizational resources, and behavior contrary to social responsibility (Oman, 2001). If these purposes are to be generalized, the following results are reached (Aktan, 2013:160):

- To prevent the business management from misusing their duties to gain benefits,
- Protecting the rights of stakeholders,

- Ensuring equal and fair treatment of the parties to the organization,
- Observing and securing the rights of all parties of the organization (such as shareholders, stakeholders, personnel, suppliers),
- Sharing the activity reports and financial situation of the organization with the public in a timely and complete manner and ensuring transparency,
- Identifying the problems of the top management of the organization clearly,
- Having an obligation to be accountable to its stakeholders for the decisions and activities of the top management of the organization,
- attorney's fees,
- Ensuring the distribution of the profit of the organization to the stakeholders and parties of the organization in proportion to their rights,
- Preventing the right of the large share to buy the small share according to the ratio of the shareholders in the organization,
- Reducing the capital costs of long-term loyal stakeholders and building organizational trust by prioritizing other sources of finance of the organization.
- To fully understand the expectation of the stakeholder from the organization and to control it by determining the rules.
- As can be understood from the objectives we have outlined, corporate governance is based on the protection of the rights of all parties, ensuring equality between the parties, transparency, the necessity of accountability, responsibility and trust.

2.2. Public Relations Concept

Let's define the concept of public relations through two concepts: "public" and "relations". The concept of people is a group of people living in a geographical area, regardless of their material and spiritual status, religion, race and gender. The concept of relationship, on the other hand, is a form of communication established between at least two people or parties, either temporarily or indefinitely, written-verbally or non-verbally. When these two concepts are evaluated together, there is no definition that can be put into a certain mold like the concept of corporate governance. Due to the flexibility of this concept in many disciplines, it is not possible to

determine a general theory. in English “ Public Relations ”, French “ Relations ” The English translation of the concept which is “ publiques ” is “public relations” and the French translation is “public relations ” . In both translations, "relationship" expresses the same thing, while the "public" hand signifies "public, public", that is, a plural group, mass, community. When this concept is examined in Turkish, “people” does not mean “human community in a country” as in TDK , but “human community that is affected by organizations or affects organizations with their behaviors” (Güven, 2013). Again, if we interpret the concept of "relation" in terms of public relations, it is interpreted as "the attitude between the organization and its target audience, which provides economic, political and cultural benefits to all parties and is interpreted with a mutually positive view" (Ledingham & Bruning 1998).

There are researchers who say that the history of public relations dates back to ancient times. Management is in question where the human races have the instinct to live together, produce and organize. This management requires communication and persuasion activities. It is thought that the motivation to manage the masses in this way laid the foundations of this concept (Yağmurlu, 2018). It is possible to refer to its history in Turkey to the Ottoman Empire. For example, it is possible to refer directly to the Ottoman Empire with the people of the sultans. For example, the sultans' dealing with their people, listening to problems, meetings in mosques, establishment of notable councils, listening to groups such as divan meetings and management styles are shown as examples. In 1961, in the post-Republic period, the representation branch of the SPO was opened. 1964 Population Planning, 1966 the first public relations course was given at Alaaddin Asna Ankara Faculty of Political Sciences, 1967 the Administrative Counseling Center, which corresponds to the current CIMER application, was established. 1982 He became the Head of the Press and Public Relations Department (Selvi, Ulucan & Coşgun , 2019).

Today, it is seen as a professional group as it is around the world. However, there are numerous definitions. Known as the father of public relations, Edward Louis Bernays public relations said, “The conscious and intelligent manipulation of the organized habits and ideas of the masses is an important element in a democratic society. We are governed, our minds, tastes and ideas are shaped. This is a result of the way our democratic society is organized. Whatever

attitude you choose towards this situation, it remains a fact that we are dominated by a relatively small number of people in politics or business, in our social behavior or ethical thinking, in almost every action of our daily lives (Bernays , 1928). Grunig and Hunt (1984) “Public relations is the distinctive management function that helps to establish and maintain mutual communication, acceptance and cooperation between an institution and its public; includes problem and issue management; helps management keep informed and respond to the public; defines and emphasizes the responsibility of management to serve the public interest; it serves as an early warning system to anticipate trends, helping management learn about new developments and bring about change effectively, and uses reliable and ethical communication techniques and research as essential tools” (Grunig and Hunt , 1984). Cutlip , Center, and Broom defined public relations as “a management function that establishes and maintains mutually beneficial relationships between the organization and the various publics on which the success or failure of an organization depends”. (Cutlip , Center & Broom , 1994). According to Baskin , Aranoff , and Lattimore , “Public relations is a management function that helps achieve organizational goals, define philosophy, and facilitate organizational change. Public relations practitioners communicate with all relevant internal and external publics to develop positive relationships and create harmony between organizational goals and social expectations. Public Relations practitioners develop, implement and evaluate organizational programs that foster the exchange of influence and understanding among all units and publics of an organization” (Baskin , Aranoff & Lattimore , 1997).

Peltekoğlu (2007) defines public relations as “strategic communication management, which is built on the objectives of the institution and carried out with target audiences whose order of importance varies according to the objectives of the institution and the campaign, such as consumers, distributors and employees” (Peltekoğlu, 2007). The Public Relations Association of America (PRSA) defines public relations as “a strategic communication process that establishes mutually beneficial relationships between organizations and their people” (PRSA, 2021), while the Australian Public Relations Institute (PRIA) defines public relations as “mutual relations between an organization and its peoples” (PRSA, 2021). It is a deliberate, planned and continuous effort to create understanding” (PRIA, 2021). The Chartered Institute

of Public Affairs (CIPR), founded by the UK Privy Council, “Public Relations is about reputation, it is the result of what you do, what you say and what others say about you. Public Relations is the discipline that respects reputation with the aim of gaining understanding and support and influencing ideas and behaviour. It is the planned and sustained effort to establish and maintain goodwill and mutual understanding between an organization and its peoples” (CIPR, 2021).

As can be seen from the definitions made, it has been seen that the order is "Group = communication, form of agreement, management function = benefit, ethics = public opinion spokesperson, early warning system, trust, reputation". It is possible to define the concept of communication between groups as "it is a management function that regulates the relations between the parties of the organizations, cares about the ideas of the parties, gives confidence and aims to provide benefits for the organization, is an early warning system for the organization and protects the reputation of the organization".

Every organization's "people" segment is different. For example; For countries, the people are the people living in that country, for a gas station they are car owners, for a book publisher they are literate, for an organization, the staff in the organization is its target audience and potential investors. It is possible to list the public relations segment for an organization as follows (Seitel , 2004): Academia, the press, auditors, shareholders, government members, public opinion leaders, staff, staff's families, competitors and vendors.

2.2.1. Basic Principles of Public Relations

There is diversity in the principles of public relations as in the diversity in the definition. The generally accepted principles are listed as follows (Kılıç, 2006; Özkan, 2009; Sabuncuoğlu, 2001):

Openness: It is the sharing of information about the organization, such as the objectives of the organization, its financial structure and status, products, market share and areas, social

activities, with the target audience in an open and transparent manner. With a transparent management approach, the organization should openly express not only what it does but also what it cannot do. This behavior is a great trust gaining behavior for the organization.

Providing Accurate Information: It is one of the most basic principles. The success of public relations practitioners is directly proportional to their giving correct information. It is important to reflect the mistakes in the organization correctly, even if it is to the detriment of the organization, and to prevent the damage that will occur later. It should not be forgotten that untrue information will damage the reputation of the organization and shorten the life of the organization. The purpose of this principle is not to show the organization different from what it is, but to make it accepted as it is.

Company Image: What people think about the organization. They are the ideas and impressions formed in the minds of people about how the organization behaves in the competitive conditions, social responsibilities, products, attitudes towards its employees, and what they do. Organizations that create a good image find public support more easily from any crisis or possible mismanagement problems. This image can be supported by public relations activities, in addition to symbols, logos, colors, visual advertisements and sensory music.

Building Two-Way Relationship: Public relations is the bridge between the organization and the audience outside the organization. While trying to carry out public relations activities within the organization, it tries to respond to the expectations, requests and complaints of the audience outside the organization. While public relations is the spokesperson of the mass outside the organization, it is the spokesperson of the organization outside the organization. Thus, a well-managed public relations management will establish a permanent long-lasting bond between the two parties by meeting the expectations of both parties, responding and producing solutions.

Credibility: It is the most difficult principle of trust-based public relations to be won in the long run. The mass outside the organization must believe in the messages given by the organization and be convinced of the activities of the organization. It is important that these messages are prepared in a clear, simple, real, reliable and consistent manner.

Being Patient and Determined: Building public trust is a process that takes a long time and requires patience. It is necessary for public relations practitioners to obtain sufficient information about the public. The culture, religious beliefs, attitudes and behaviors, traditions and habits of the society should be determined well and the organization should adapt to these conditions. This process requires good planning, determination, budget, fieldwork and determination.

Widespread Responsibility: The success of the work of the public relations practitioner of the organization will be possible if each unit and individual in the organization adopts these responsibilities and fulfills the requirements of their responsibilities. It should not be forgotten that every unit and every individual in the organization is a representative of the organization.

3. Fields of Activity of Public Relations

Wherever there is a human community, there is public relations. The scope of activities of this concept, which takes place in many disciplines, is also quite wide. It is possible to list these areas as follows (Tellan , 2011 ; Geçikli , 2017):

- **Following Environmental Factors: It should** constantly update itself. It should constantly revise itself by following economic trends, social changes, political processes, technological changes and competitors.
- **Consultancy:** It provides guidance and advice on every situation that is the subject of public relations, such as the internal processes, target groups, practices, competition policies of organizations.

- **Event Management:** It organizes events to promote organizations or their products and innovations to the public. For example; fairs, exhibitions, cocktails, conferences, etc.
- **Financial Relations:** They establish positive relations with the organization's investors, financial environment, and potential investors by communicating with them.
- **Public Relations:** On behalf of their organizations, leaders in the public sector communicate with politicians.
- **Crisis Management:** Motivates the organization by supporting solutions in the face of possible disaster scenarios. They communicate well by managing the audience outside the organization.
- **Corporate Public Relations:** It provides a stronger and more accurate representation of the organization's image in front of the masses.
- **Cross-Cultural Communication:** Represents the organization and communicates between different cultures.
- **Relations with the Media:** It informs and promotes all kinds of press officials in local, national and international organizations operating in the written, visual, audio media and social networks of the organization.
- **Copywriting:** Provides communication by creating messages according to groups of audiences (such as age, gender, interests).
- **Internal Communication:** It provides communication with the mass within the organization. Listens to their expectations, complaints and suggestions, takes into account, organizes events when necessary.
- **Inter-Organizational Communication:** It enables the organization to communicate with its suppliers, market competitors and potential business partners.
- **Strategic Relations:** By identifying the issues and problems that may affect the organization in the competitive environment, it can offer solutions for the purpose.
- **Social Communication:** They communicate with their representatives for the future of the organization and society. They identify their expectations and problems and offer solutions.
- **Social Responsibility:** They produce social responsibility projects for the future of the society.

Aims and Importance of Public Relations

It is thought that public relations is a management style based on trust and communication. It has a two-way communication, social and organizational. Therefore, it is possible to evaluate the purposes of public relations in two ways (Gelikli , 2017). Organizational and social objectives of public relations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Organizational and Social Objectives of Public Relations

Organizational Purposes	Social Purposes
Gaining organizational prestige	Openness and transparency in organizational policies
Gaining audience trust	Building trust in the organization
Encourage entrepreneurship	Communication tool between the public and the organization
Sister organizations win	requests, complaints, suggestions and setting expectations
Adapting to change	True to the demands of society providing management
Getting potential investors	Public service when necessary support on
Acquiring qualified personnel	According to the education level of the society revising policies

As seen in Table 1, public relations focused on the relations between the organization and the society. Transparency, openness and harmony are expected in the face of mutual trust, understanding, communication, respect. An established organizational culture and image earns respect. The best way to achieve this is to make the target audience feel like they are a part of

this organization. It is possible to do this by taking into account the wishes and complaints and in the form of feedback that they are taken into account, but thanks to the developing technology and social networks, it is now possible to do it online instantly. Reaching the public and collecting information from the public has become easier than before. While it is easier to get feedback at any time, it is also easier to collect the reaction of the public and to record the slightest mistake. For this reason, public relations should be analyzed more carefully than before and should be more careful about the right steps.

The importance of communication between organizations and society is inevitable. The people of the organization better express their understanding of it and the message "you are our family" in the advertisements it publishes to give information about its products. While the poor management of advertisements, which is a public relations tool, can prevent the organization from achieving its purpose and cause great losses, a well-managed public relations can provide great gains. If we give a few examples on this subject (Canbaz , 2020):

- **Food Company:** The organization's April 1 themed commercial contains slogans such as “The time of reckoning is approaching”, “I will have surprises for you”. The main theme of the ad is that younger siblings who are oppressed by their older siblings take revenge on the older siblings through jokes. However, the reason for the advertisement to be criticized is the political elections to be held in the country on the same dates. The slogans were perceived by the public for political purposes and the organization received a great reaction from the public. After this reaction, the organization was fined because of the advertisement film, which did not remain silent in law.
- **Soda Company:** The organization has an international structure and wanted to advertise a sugar-free product. The organization investigating why the product, which is mostly bought by women, is not bought by men because of the writing of " light " on the product , has determined that the sales of the product are low due to the misconception of the word " light " by men in our country. The organization changed the name of the same product to “ zero ” in order to destroy this perception and ensure that the product was bought by men, and offered it for sale with a commercial that created the image of “men in black” by changing the color of the product to black. This change has led to an

increase in sales figures for the product. Even though it is not a national beverage, the same company is a reason for preference with its commercial films that touch the emotions on religious holidays and days.

- **Toy Company:** This organization, which is a toy manufacturer, released a commercial for the New Year with the slogan "Don't Look For Fun Outside on New Year's Eve!". The advertisement film garnered reactions with the messages in the advertisement giving rape and sexist messages. In the face of these reactions, the company apologized and canceled the commercial.
- Due to the Covid-19 outbreak, a Japanese store "Takeya" has made it mandatory for all its employees to wear masks, as it is all over the world. However, it has been determined that the mask prevents the use of mimics, which is an important part of the communication of the employees with their customers. Thereupon, the company launched the "Smile Campaign". The aim of the campaign is to enable employees to re-establish warm and sincere relations with customers. The company, which printed smiling lip figures on the masks of its employees, thus formed a warmer bond with the public.

Tools Used in Public Relations

The most important mechanism of public relations is communication. It provides communication with its parties through some means. These tools facilitate communication within and outside the organization. Looking at the literature, the classification among instruments is divided into three parts. These tools, which are divided into three parts as mass, one-to-one and organizational communication, can be divided into three groups as written, sensory and face-to-face when it comes to a deeper distinction.

Each organization uses whichever tool is more appropriate within its own body. It is possible to classify all of these tools as internal and external to the organization. Even if this distinction is made in the literature, it is now possible to design many of these products for use outside the organization as well as within the organization due to developing technology and conditions .

For example , while it is possible to broadcast a radio broadcast in the organization for internal motivation , this broadcast is made outside the organization and reaches customers.

Duties of Public Relations

The fact that organizations include a public relations person is related to factors such as the structure of the organization, field of activity, geographical location, sector. The ways in which public relations are assigned vary according to the structures of the organizations. Units can consist of one person, or they can consist of many units and people. It is important for these established units to be able to cope with the problems that may arise in the organization in a fast and reliable way, to establish a good and fast communication network, and to be solution-oriented. If we summarize the duties of public relations, they can be listed as follows (Akdağ, 2007):

- Analyzing the target audience.
- To provide reliable, open and transparent information about the organization to the target audience.
- To direct the management of the organization by adopting the goals of the organization well and making long-term plans in this direction.
- To make intra-period evaluations by analyzing the plans made.
- It should take necessary measures or make updates on what needs to be done by making regular audience assessments.
- He should regularly evaluate the organization and its environment and make observations for possible problems.
- The organization must create an identity.
- The organization should create an image and try to gain the trust of the target audience.
- It should use public relations tools effectively and efficiently to reach the target audience.
- In positive or possible negative situations, it should ensure that news and information are included in the media when needed.

- Organize events (exhibition, fair, conference, etc.) in order to closely follow the target audience.
- Events should be organized, celebrations should be held, small awards should be made on birthdays, and organizations such as tournaments should be organized in order to get closer with the internal staff and create a sense of belonging. The families of the staff should be included in these activities from time to time .

He/she should attend and represent the invitations on behalf of the organization.

The public relations practitioner should be especially equipped with sociology, psychology and law, and should defend his unit and organization with the support of these subjects when necessary.

In general, the duties of a public relations person are as above. Having a public relations person in the organization is advantageous for the organization, but in some cases it can also harm the organization. The advantages and disadvantages of a public relations person within the organization are as follows (Kılıç, 2006, p.27):

Advantages:

- Public relations practitioners are always in the organization and know the organization very well, interpret it and know its needs. It acts as a buffer in case of need, and leaves a practitioner who takes care of it, even if the practitioner is not in the organization.
- Public relations practitioners are selected from qualified people and are well equipped about the sector.
- It establishes a good communication network within the organization, is fast and reliable.
- Since the public relations unit is close to the executive rooms, information is easily accessible and the practitioner can intervene immediately in case of emergency.
- Public relations practitioners are equipped to offer daily advice and suggestions to the management.
- Public relations practitioners are responsible for the press and act as spokespersons for the organization.

- Since public relations practitioners are constantly in the organization, they have a large share in the success of the organization and their loyalty to the organization is complete.

Disadvantages:

- Public relations practitioners may lose their objectivity because they are very close to the management and the organization. If the press realizes this, public confidence may be damaged.
- If public relations practitioners are not well trained and qualified, they may make decisions that will harm the organization.
- Public relations practitioners may not be qualified for managerial qualifications.
- Management may not be able to reach consensus on the job descriptions of public relations practitioners.
- Another alternative is to recruit a public relations practitioner from outside the organization. There will be some advantages and disadvantages to the organization in this provision, they can be listed as follows:

Advantages:

- It will always be objective.
- As he can provide consultancy to many sectors, he will be able to offer different perspectives.
- The organization will be able to manage the media better than internal public relations practitioners. Because it will be in contact with a larger and wider media audience than it can provide consultancy to many sectors.
- He has good communication with technical places (translator, photography, etc.) so he is more talented and makes good presentations.
- Organizational loyalty is as long as the contract period.

Disadvantages:

- Since it is from outside, it may not be able to adapt to the target audience immediately.

- Since the unit will work with a limited number of people, internal communication may slow down.
- Performance is directly proportional to the amount of pay.
- If the consultant has no previous experience in the organization's industry, there may be a slowdown in public relations while learning.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

"Business management", which is a concept that was born in order to cope with the problems such as corruption, informal economy, and inequality of competition, which the working life does not want to happen all over the world, but constantly encounters, is a concept that makes a positive contribution to the working life based on fairness, transparency, accountability and responsibility. The concept of corporate governance provides organizations with the opportunity to grow together with their shares and stakeholders, not alone. Studies show that organizations that adopt business management have a longer life expectancy than organizations that do not. However, since it is a behavioral concept, it is not clear whether the reports submitted or the relevance are complete. Between September 2004 and February 2005, the Corporate Governance Association of Turkey wanted to conduct a field study called "Corporate Governance Map of Turkey". Questionnaire forms were sent to 1000 organizations for the survey to be evaluated for "suitability" and "performance", and only 123 organizations were returned (TKYD, 2005: 4). Likewise, for this study, 125 organizations were sent and 2 positive responses were received. The fact that many studies that can be cited as examples like this have such low returns, and the organizations' avoidance of surveys in response to the reports they announce to the public, undoubtedly arouses curiosity about the accuracy of the reports.

The concept has been subjected to many criticisms, such as the dissatisfaction of those outside the management network, delays in the approval of decisions due to the final decision being left to the board of directors, reconciliation problems due to the overcrowding of the management, problems in the determination of the responsible persons due to the crowded management. Corporate Governance Association of Turkey and StrategyCo . The data obtained

from the results of 30 managers and approximately 300 forms published by the company in January 2015 are as follows in the “Corporate Governance Perception Research Report” (TKYD, 2015);

- Organization managers think that their authority and responsibilities will decrease when the transition to corporate governance will be made, and they ignore corporate governance in order not to give up control.
- Unless company owners are convinced of corporate governance, it is difficult to move to corporate governance.
- Corporate governance creates a financial and operational shield and protects organizations in times of crisis.
- Transitions are slow as there is no government coercion.
- Organizations should determine their own time for transition to corporate management and they should pass the time that is most appropriate for them. Again, when the same report and the literature are examined, it is seen that organizations do not have information about business management other than CMB data. Looking at the data of this research, it has been determined that the links between the years of professional experience and corporate governance in the organization are weak, and the lack of information on corporate governance within the organization has been identified.

It has been observed that there is a need for both boards of directors and in-organization trainings in this regard. It has been seen that there are 5 modules in the executive and in-organization trainings published by the "Global Corporate Governance Forum (GCGF)" in 2003 and it is thought that giving these trainings in our country will be beneficial in terms of corporate governance. The content of the trainings ; Why do we train managers ?, Managers' roles in the organization, preparing a business plan, dealing with difficult situations, funding sources, forming a board of directors, selecting senior staff, developing a charter, establishing codes of conduct, Income generating extra services and activities, social responsibility plans, Budget and financial planning, risk and internal controls, performance measurement, sustainability (GCGF, 2003).

Another concept that business management has been likened to recently is public relations. There are slight differences between the two concepts, which seem to serve the same purpose when we look at the basics. Both concepts are universal, they do not have a clear definition and are shaped according to the organization. The equality principle of corporate governance and the two-way relationship principle of public relations are semantically similar. Likewise, the principles of transparency and openness, accountability and providing accurate information, responsibility and the principle of widespread responsibility are similar. While agency theory regulates the relations between management and stakeholder; The authority of representation regulates the relations with the administration and all the masses (such as states, target audience, share, stakeholders). As they serve the same purpose, they also have the same ethical ethics as organizational ethics.

Based on the research, the following recommendations can be made:

In order to prevent the lack of knowledge in organizations about business management and to raise awareness of corporate governance, the management of the organization and all parties involved in the organization should be trained with the training titles shown below and which can be revised from organization to organization.

department or do not include it in the organization, due to the fact that human resources come to the fore in organizations and it is easier to reach the public through social media with the developing technology . It can be suggested that this unit, which analyzes public relations by communicating with the public with different perspectives and different techniques, should come to the forefront in organizations and give the necessary importance and authority.

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